

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP9

D9.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

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LENSES Dissemination and Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

The present document details the LENSES project dissemination and communication strategy, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. CREA is lead partner and responsible for designing and implementing LENSES communication and dissemination strategy, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

An effective communication and dissemination strategy can facilitate a coherent and sustainable communication of the project, and ensure that the projects' objectives, aims, results and final products and outcomes are disseminated to all relevant target audiences, stakeholders and public authorities on the EU-, national-, and regional levels.

The further explained strategy is then transferred to action items (campaigns, events, workshops, webinars, etc. and their timings) in order to achieve the best impact of the project results.

The strategy will be monitored and updated in a later project phase in order to apply methodologies to ensure the highest transferability and visibility of LENSES results in a long-time run.

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LENSES Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Introduction

LENSES aspires to create a **WEF Nexus narrative and Call to Action**. The core message of this narrative is the **paradigm shift from Nexus Thinking to Resilient Nexus Doing** for strengthening resilience. To this end, the project will reach out to a general public with visual tools to create an awareness of the WEF Nexus, the interactions among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation - in a cross-cutting manner) and their impact, as well as the potential to create new socio-economic opportunities.

In order to maximise impact, the communication and dissemination (C&D) strategy will focus on publicizing concrete results and positive feedback loops created by the participatory development and application of LENSES principles by the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) in the pilots (see WP2). These results will be used to further advertise the potential of LENSES in informing and shaping policy, helping to break down silos among the four domains and overcome Nexus “inertia”.

Dissemination activities will showcase the methodological and practical innovations of the project, as well as, crucially, how these elements are becoming transformative tools in the hands of local stakeholders, rooted in the LAAs, catalyzing change not only in terms of end products (e.g. a basin water management plan), but also in terms of building cross-sectoral relationships of collaboration and trust among all relevant stakeholders.

For this purpose, this document effectively defines key communication and dissemination strategy elements such as **objectives, targeted audiences, key messages, general rules for C&D activities, channels and tools, and events**. At the local pilot level, it aims to create Nexus awareness and promote the growth and work of LAAs. By providing visibility to LAA actions, for example through the use of digital and social media, it will provide an added incentive for partners to participate, as well as inspire other LAAs across pilot areas. As the LAAs activities grow, in tandem with the development of the LENSES tools and solutions, their activities and results will be promoted in a gradually broader but also specialized audience, including national planning agencies, local and national government, financial as well other key institutions and stakeholders. This final version of the communication and dissemination strategy has used inputs from the stakeholder mapping in WP2 and the stakeholder & institutional analysis in WP3 to more specifically define the target audiences. This supports more efficient and tailored external communication actions (e.g. policy briefs to selected audiences), the use of the most appropriate channels (owned media, events) and tools (hard copy or digital, videos, etc.), as well as the definition of a time plan of actions and quantitative targets. A multi-channel and multi-media approach have been used to increase outreach and efficacy of all communication and dissemination activities.

1. Key Communication and Dissemination Elements

1.1 Objectives

The communication and dissemination strategy aims to:

- ❖ **improve the awareness** of local stakeholders, policy and decision makers and general public of the Mediterranean Area on the latest knowledge and experiences available on the WEF Nexus, on how it relates to multi-level and multi-scale stakeholders and on the benefits and opportunities that it can bring to local communities in the beneficiary countries;
- ❖ **maximize visibility and networking of LENSES** across all audiences, via different media;
- ❖ promote **LENSES** and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner;
- ❖ **inform, support and improve the decision-making processes** towards the capitalization and adoption of the NEXUS approaches, ultimately **fostering the development of national and regional policy framework**, by raising awareness among relevant stakeholders and decision makers on the cross-sectoral benefits of LENSES proposed approaches;
- ❖ facilitate **knowledge and information exchange** with other thematically related projects and networks.

The communication and dissemination strategy is **results-driven** in order to influence the stakeholders (e.g. farmers associations) and policy decision-makers at different scales, from local to national, regional, and international level. Instead of following a simple sender-receiver model of communication, where the addressed are seen as passive recipients, target groups will be approached as self-determined and self-responsible persons who are actively searching and processing information in an individual way. Therefore, LENSES communication is organized as a dynamic, two-way process that involves participation and feedback loops. This approach is embedded in the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs – WP2) and will constitute the basic strategy in the implementation of the project pilot cases (WP8), ultimately working as a driver in identifying and supporting the finalization of WP9 (Pathways to impact).

1.2 Target audiences

In order to be effective, the design of dissemination activities and communication processes is tailor-made to get through identified multilevel **target groups** (see Table 1). This approach adequately considers their interests, information needs, pre-existing state of knowledge, values, and perceptions as well as the social, cultural and institutional contexts within they are acting. The target groups will be well defined, as the choice of the communication tools, communication style and language together with the communication channels to be calibrated to each specific situation. Besides target groups within the countries where LENSES is implemented, other relevant groups will be identified. In fact, the **communication of project experience to other interested parties** is fundamental to foster the opportunities for replicating lessons learned in other contexts and geographical areas. For this reason, project partners will rely on the competencies and the networks of stakeholders of the External Advisory Board and of REXUS project.

Table 1 Identified multilevel target groups to address within LENSES

Target Audience (WHO)	Dissem. Measures (WHAT)	Dissem. Activities (HOW-WHEN)	Expected Impact (AREA)
Public Authorities & Policy Makers	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, Policy briefs, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 LAA Regional meetings + 1 intra-project LAA (from M8) • 6 Project plenary meetings (M1-36) • LENSES learning platform (from M6, updated) • 2 Nexus e-dialogue webinars for dissemination in pilots (M20-34) • 2 technical webinars (M20-34) • Project website, social media and Serious Game (from M6) • Participation to selected external events and networking activities • Replication Guide (M36) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced understanding of Nexus interactions to achieve Nexus resilience • Support to evidence-based policy design • Enhanced capacity to select appropriate solutions using the LENSES toolset
Asset Owners	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, Newsletters, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above • Social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn), YouTube videos • LENSES Stories (podcasts & short videos) for storytelling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced understanding of Nexus interactions • Increased awareness of Nexus Solutions • Improved cooperation through co-creation and co-ownership through LAAs
River Basin/ Water Management bodies	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, Newsletters, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergies with other regional and cross regional processes and initiatives • Increased outreach to signatories of international conventions and member states of regional Processes
Farmers, Water Users Associations, Relevant Associations, participants in LAAs	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, Newsletters, Social Media, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased awareness on Nexus interactions and multiple benefits • Opportunities for funding replication and upscaling of LENSES solutions
International Organisations & Processes	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, Policy briefs, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution of new knowledge in a complex theme • Opportunities for knowledge exchange and new collaborations
International Financial Institutions & Donors	Events, Meetings, Targeted communications, policy briefs, Replication Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased engagement in multi-stakeholder processes • Increased awareness on Nexus interactions and benefits
Research & Academia	Events, Meetings, Website, Scientific Publications, Newsletters, Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased awareness on Nexus interactions and benefits
NGOs & CSOs	Events, Meetings, Website, Newsletters, Social Media, Serious Game	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nexus demystified in simple language and with visuals • Understanding of how LENSES contributes to sustainable development
Media & press (local, national, EU & Med)	Media releases, Website, Social Media, Serious Game	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	
General Public	Website, Social Media, Serious Game	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above 	

1.3 Key messages

The general objective of LENSES is to contribute to **improved water allocation, enhanced food security while preserving ecosystems and aiding climate change adaptation**, by supporting the operationalization of the Nexus paradigm (**from Nexus Thinking to Nexus Doing**) through a collective learning process, which integrates the concepts of sustainable Nexus management (progressing Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs) with a resilience-oriented approach, leading decision-makers in accepting uncertainty as integral part of management and decision-making.

LENSES aims to the following **specific objectives**:

- SO.1 Identify Nexus Domain Objectives (NDO) & Nexus Resilience Qualities (NRQ) that facilitate the transition;
- SO.2 Activate Learning & Action Alliances (LAAs) to drive the Nexus dialogue;
- SO.3 Develop Participatory System Dynamics Models (PSDM) to support evidence-based policy design;
- SO.4 Co-design scenarios to test WEF Nexus resilience;
- SO.5 Carry out Ecosystem Services (ESS) assessments to inform multi-objective policies and measures;
- SO.6 Assess and manage interdependences between Nexus and SDGs;
- SO.7 Improve Natural Governance and align WEF policies toward Nexus management;
- SO.8 Build Nexus business cases using environmental and ecological economics;
- SO.9 Plan Nature-based Solutions (NBS) measures to co-achieve multiple DOs.

In this context, the communication and dissemination strategy has a key role.

Project key messages are:

- a. **The implementation of NEXUS approaches can produce multiple benefits for local populations** (e.g. save natural resources, provide support to preserve and restore ecosystems, offer opportunities for developing resilience to climate change thus supporting food security): there are both scientific evidences and experiences around the world which demonstrate that. Furthermore, raising awareness through the direct involvement of stakeholders in modelling is crucial to value these benefits, which will ultimately contribute to local socio-economic development.
- b. There are some **positive experiences of implementation of NEXUS in some Mediterranean countries (LENSES Pilot areas) which represent best practices to widespread**. These experiences can be used as a model to adapt to specific contexts in other countries.
- c. **Policy-makers can support the spreading of NEXUS approaches and the operationalization of the Nexus paradigm** (from Nexus Thinking to Nexus Doing) by incorporating specific measures in the sectoral policies of their countries. Furthermore, LENSES will contribute to better understand the cross-sectoral implications of sectoral policies, thus activating a real nexus approach.

The knowledge transfer and communication perspective are integrated throughout the entire project cycle (e.g. via bringing scientific and technological competences to the project participants, via supporting and counselling pilot activities in different countries, and via guiding design of communication events).

During the first year of project implementation, each partner has adapted the three above mentioned key messages to the local conditions and needs and has chosen the tuned key messages and specific communication tools to be used in implementation of local and regional events.

The **list of key messages to be spread by Pilot managers** during the first year's local events has been updated along the project lifespan, to incorporate new key messages related to the project achievements and lessons learned. For example, some pilots are conveying that their work is focusing on operationalizing the Nexus at a local scale to provide evidence that can be later upscaled and can inform policy with well documented examples of best practices.

1.4 General rules for project communication and dissemination activities

All LENSES communication and dissemination products will comply with the GA requirements, and respectively with art. **38.1.2 Information on PRIMA funding — Obligation and right to use the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem**; and art. **29.4 Information on PRIMA funding — Obligation and right to use the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem**. Therefore, unless the PRIMA Foundation requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication and dissemination (in any form, including electronic) will:

- (a) display the PRIMA logo
- (b) display the EU emblem;
- (c) include the following text;

“This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union”.

When displayed together with another logo, the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem will have appropriate prominence.

Furthermore, all LENSES communication and dissemination products will include, according to Art. **29.5 Disclaimer excluding the PRIMA Foundation responsibility** of the GA, the following sentence: “This publication reflects only the author's view and the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”.

2. Communication and dissemination channels and tools

Communication activities have been following an integrated approach, creating a mix of news and learning from the LENSES approach, shared on various **digital channels** (website, social media platforms), powered by social media campaigns and **targeted communications with decision makers and key stakeholders** aspiring to instigate a mind shift toward Nexus Thinking and Doing vs. sectoral approaches (see Table 2).

Emphasis has been laid on **digital and virtual events and materials**, in order to achieve maximum possible inclusion, reduce costs and greenhouse emissions as well as a risk-mitigation strategy against the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. **A series of 2 webinars** will disseminate the results and learnings from the LENSES approach in the pilot sites, in partnership with LAAs (M20-30). In addition, **2 Nexus e-dialogues** will discuss replication potential in different contexts. **Key communication and dissemination events** will be held as virtual, in-person and hybrid meetings. The **closing event** will feature success stories from the pilot cases, their results and their exploitation roadmap. Project results will be shared via the project website (<https://www.lenses-prima.eu/outcomes/>) as well as through webinars, e-dialogues, social media campaigns, blog, publications and participation in various international, national and local conference and events.

Table 2 Planned Communication and Dissemination Activities

Visual identity	Content development	Curation	Events	Knowledge creating and sharing	Stakeholder engagement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key visual • LENSES logo • Typeface • Templates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roll-up, Brochure, Poster, Power point, factsheets • Website • LENSES serious game • Short videos • Storylines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website feed • Social media • Storytelling • Press release 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional events • Closing public events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars/e-dialogues • Social media • Publications • Replication guide • Podcasts • Blog 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder engagement meetings • Targeted direct communications with authorities and policy makers

High-quality contents on WEF Nexus have been developed, capitalizing on existing sources from previous Nexus projects (Sim4Nexus, Magic Nexus, etc.), introducing audiences in simple terms to the potential of the approach, as well as the obstacles, further presenting the novel approach presented by LENSES and the opportunities that lie ahead.

The project has developed a distinct **visual identity** (logo, key visuals) and **identity material** (brochure, poster, roll up, etc.). The dedicated **project website** and **accounts on social media** platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) features the necessary background info on the WEF Nexus and the project itself, and area source of live information on project developments, including, crucially, the evaluation of the pilots, the development of the LAAs and how Nexus policy can be catalyzed through the LENSES approach. The focus will be on presenting at once an innovative integrative tool with the potential to transform policy and produce new solutions on the ground, while at the same time bringing to the fore the human, social and

institutional actors taking part in and driving the change on the ground, providing the actual case studies (stories of collaboration, of trust-building, of adopting novel approaches to jointly examine old problems in a new light), and eventually to be replicated. **Videos** and other **storytelling** formats will be used to highlight the value of these results in an easily shareable format. Storytelling represents as a powerful tool of communication that can be engaging, memorable, provide context and relevance, can be more persuasive than data alone and is a testimonial for impact. **Stories** help connecting the challenge with the solutions, featuring how real people select the most appropriate solutions to address challenges, utilizing LENSES toolset to yield multi-fold benefits. Stories generated among the LAAs on how the LENSES approach was applied in each case can easily be shared among LAAs, peers and decision makers, along with their experience and learnings. Also, **success stories from case studies** and their impact to inspire replication and scaling up of solutions piloted will be documented in the form of interviews, narratives that can be adapted in size, podcasts and short videos and disseminated to a wide audience.

This section gives an overview of the visual identity, digital channels and main tools developed to maximize the efficacy of LENSES communication and dissemination activities.

2.1 Visual identity

The visual identity created for the LENSES project aims to facilitate the design and implementation of all communication and dissemination activities and tools to be realized within the project in order to ensure an effective transfer of project results and know-how to various target audiences. Furthermore, the visual identity of the project provides a solid basis to develop professionally crafted project identity materials to facilitating an optimal dissemination and exploitation of the project's results.

A series of project identity materials - respecting LENSES visual identity- has been created. These include a project key visual, a project logo, several templates and communication products, as well as the project website, with the core aim to inform the different stakeholders and the wide public in general about the project. The most relevant characteristics of the above mentioned visual identity elements are summarized in the following sub-sections, as they are basic components of the communication and dissemination strategy adopted in LENSES. Nevertheless, for a more comprehensive and detailed description of the project visual identity, please refer to [D9.2 Visual identity and project identity material](#) which is available as public deliverable in the section "Outcomes" of the project website.

2.1.1. Key visual

A key visual has been developed to serve as a brand for LENSES to enhance the recognition of the project. The LENSES visual key consists in overlapping intersected waves symbolizing the dynamic interaction among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation) of the Nexus as well as the cross-cutting approach uses to look at them in the context of LENSES. The brand recognition is ensured as the intersected waves are coherently reused on the website and all other communication and dissemination products.

Intersected waves, representing the four domains of the Nexus, have been colored in four colors (blue, green, yellow and white – Fig.1, parts "a" and "b") or by using colored related textures (Fig.1, part "c").

Figure 1 LENSES Key visual. Three versions of the intersected waves used. The overlapping waves are symbolizing the dynamic interaction among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation) of the Nexus as well as the cross-cutting approach uses to look at them in the context of LENSES.

2.1.2. LENSES logo

Figure 2 LENSES project logo

A project logo (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**) was designed to make the LENSES project easily recognizable. The LENSES logo is:

1. Easy to recognize, to be reduced or enlarged (size flexibility);
2. Easy to apply to different media tools (printouts, animation, web-design, ...);
3. Easy to reproduce by needlework for preparing promotional items;

4. Printable both in color and in black and white only.

The logo of the project has been used in all internal and external documents that the project produces to communicate about activities and results.

2.1.3. LENSES Templates

LENSES has a strong focus on the local dimension. Consequently, most communication activities concentrate on this dimension and should be necessarily tailored on the specific needs of the people involved in pilot activities, which vary largely among different Regions. For this reason, the partners decided to prepare templates for communication and dissemination purposes that can be easily adapted to specific needs and occasions. A number of templates, labelled with LENSES, EU and PRIMA Foundation's logos, have been prepared and made available for all partners in the [Partner area of the project website](#) (Figure 3). All templates can be used by all partners in English language, or, alternatively, translated into local languages according to the specific needs and activities.

Figure 3 "Partner area" web section available in the project website in which all Templates for Communication and Dissemination purposes have been made available for project partners.

The following templates have been developed:

- ❖ Agenda for events;
- ❖ Project's brochure;
- ❖ Pilot's brochure;
- ❖ MS Word/Deliverable;
- ❖ Informed consent form;
- ❖ Scientific poster;
- ❖ Press release;
- ❖ Power Point;
- ❖ Roll up.

2.2 Digital channels

2.2.1 Email account and mailing lists

For the needs of official communication, the **official email account** of LENSES project has been established in May 2021: info.lenses@crea.gov.it. This account has been included in all LENSES communication and dissemination tools, such as the project website, social media accounts, printed material etc. CREA, as the coordinator of the project, is responsible of the management of this account, while specific enquiries, comments, and requests for information will be forwarded by CREA to project partners, if needed.

So far, two **mailing lists** have been established: the first one includes all members of project partner institutions and is accessible by all partners through the “Partner area” of the project website, which is accessible upon registration (<https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partner-area/>). A second mailing list includes the members of the External Advisory Board (EAB). Materials to be distributed to EAB mailing list should be sent to CREA. Both mailing lists have been created by using Microsoft Outlook and are managed by CREA.

Further mailing lists will be established by each partner to facilitate the communication with local stakeholders, for sharing opportunities to participate in public events and any project updates, to maintain contact with the community throughout the project.

2.2.2 Project website

A dedicated project website (<http://www.lenses-prima.eu>) has been developed in October 2021 (M6) and updated on a regular basis. It will remain available online for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

The website is the first source of information about the project, therefore it contains the right information in a clear and accessible design and structure ¹. It is written in a simple language and uses clear messages that can be understood by a broad target audience. The content of the website has been organized in a way that keywords can be easily found.

The graphic layout of the website is consistent with the LENSES visual identity and includes all elements required to comply with the general rules for communication and dissemination activities of projects financed under the PRIMA Foundation programme.

The top navigation bar includes: the project title and the link to the main LENSES social channels (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn), and the logo of the project, the search function and the website menu. The menu bar gives access to 9 main web sections: Home; Summary; Pilot areas; Methodology; Outcomes; Events-Blog; Partners; Contacts and Partner area. The last page is accessible only upon registration, by members of the project *consortium*.

LENSES website homepage, its structure and main contents are represented in Figure 4 and described in the following paragraph.

¹ Pinnacle, *Project Communication Guide*, INTERREG VIC Programme, April 2012, p. 13.

Figure 4 Structure of the LENSES website homepage

The left frame of the homepage includes the logo and the link to the Contracting Authority website (<https://prima-med.org/>) and the EU emblem logo that embeds the link to EU website (https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_en). The left frame includes the logo and the link to the website of the leading partner institution (<https://www.crea.gov.it/>).

Among all the different web sections, the webpage dedicated to the [Outcomes](#) of the project is of particular interest. In fact, it includes the accesses to the following contents:

- ❖ the 2 main platforms developed in the framework of LENSES:
 - the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs); and
 - the Catalogue for Nature Based Solutions;
- ❖ the repository of public deliverables; and
- ❖ the repository of common communication and dissemination tools to be used during project-related meetings and workshops (e.g. posters, brochures).

The Learning and Action Alliance (LAAs) platform (LENSES Window) aims to facilitate, in each pilot area, the engagement of the most relevant target audiences and allies at local level. The LAAs platform will allow for a more direct contact with key stakeholders, as it will be customized for each pilot area to include chat rooms, blog, data sharing, in local language. Its development will be gradual to keep in touch with engaged stakeholders and to start a conversation that will continue in the longer term- the length of LENSES project at least.

The catalogue on Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) allows end users to identify appropriate NBS and provides them with the right Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the technical effectiveness of selected NBS. Through this platform, users can explore a list of available NBS and have access to guidelines for the development of a business model in order to make selected NBS more sustainable.

The [Summary](#) section gives an overview of the project including objectives, actors and geography, and expected results. Furthermore, it reports useful details on project funding through the table reported in Figure 5.

The [Pilot areas](#) web section gives access to LENSES map from which various sub-sections dedicated to the 7 pilot areas can be accessed. The webpage dedicated to each pilot area includes: the logo of the institution responsible for the pilot area which embeds the link to partner institution webpage within the LENSES website. At the bottom of the partner institution logo, the name of the pilot area leader is reported. On the left side, the website page gives access to the section

NAME OF THE ACTION AND ACRONYM	<i>L</i> earning and action alliances for <i>N</i> exus <i>E</i> nvironment <i>S</i> in an uncertain future - LENSES
IMPLEMENTATION PERIOD	01 May 2021 – 30 April 2024 (36 months)
GRANT AGREEMENT N°	2041
FUNDED BY	The Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area - The PRIMA Foundation
FUNDING PROGRAMME	The PRIMA programme supported by the <i>E</i> uropean <i>U</i> nion under the <i>H</i> 2020 <i>E</i> U <i>F</i> unding for <i>R</i> esearch and <i>I</i> nnovation - Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA
OVERALL BUDGET	EUR 3.482.000,00 (Three million four hundred eighty-two thousand euro)
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 2.998.000,00 (Two million nine hundred ninety-eight thousand euro)
COORDINATED BY	Council for Agricultural Research and Economics - CREA

Figure 5 LENSES funding details

“Pilot related documents” which includes the Pilot area factsheet and other dedicated C&D products developed in the framework of the project activities.

The [Partner area](#) section is accessible only by members of the project, upon registration. It includes access to five sub-sections: “Mailing list” which include the email contacts of all LENSES members; “Templates” which includes editable version of all C&D tools; “Meeting documents” (e.g. PPT presentations used during the plenary meetings); “Confidential deliverables”; and “Press kit”.

The [Events - Blog](#) section contains details and links on past and future events developed both within and outside the project and focusing on LENSES related topics. The blog main page contains the list of all posts, with the most recent ones highlighted on the top of the webpage. Each post has a preview picture and a short description of the article, whose full version is accessible by clicking on the “read more” link. The blog is frequently updated with the purpose of keeping constant the communication between the project and the stakeholders on what’s going on, let them know about news and achieved results.

The [Partner](#) section gives access to various webpages, each of it dedicated to one of the thirteen partner institutions. Each webpage dedicated to partner institution includes: the logo and the link to the homepage of the website of the partner institution; a link to access a repository of press releases launched by each partner institution at national level; details on all team members involved in the project activities. For each team member the webpage reports: a recent picture, a short biography and the role(s) covered in the LENSES project.

2.2.3 Social media accounts

LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account entitled “LENSES Prima” was created and is available at this [link](#). The LinkedIn profile page of LENSES includes an overview on the project and a link to the project website. The official LinkedIn account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

YouTube

A YouTube account entitled “LENSES Prima” was created and is available at this [link](#). The YouTube page of LENSES includes all videos developed in the context of Task 9.5 “Story as a driver of change”. The official

YouTube account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

Twitter

A Twitter account entitled “The LENSES Project” was created and is available at this [link](#). The official Twitter account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

Facebook

Facebook assures a worldwide visibility. A Facebook page entitled “The LENSES Project” was created under the Facebook account of the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA) and is available at this [link](#). The official Facebook page of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the end of the project.

This Facebook page aims to transfer the LENSES knowledge to the general public and to raise the interest of a non-specialized audience toward LENSES-related topics.

2.2.4 Videos

Short videos and other storytelling formats have been and will be produced to highlight the value of LENSES results in an easily shareable format (D9.6) and to achieve a wide audience. Storytelling represents as a powerful communication tool that can be engaging, memorable, provide context and relevance, can be more persuasive than data alone and is a testimonial for impact. Videos will be delivered through blogs, a dedicated [YouTube channel](#) and social media. The video will be recorded in local languages of all involved beneficiary countries, with subtitles in English.

2.3 Communication toolkit

A number of common communication products, including all graphic elements characterizing both the project (see [D9.2 Visual identity and project identity material](#)) and the PRIMA Foundation (e.g. the PRIMA logo, the EU emblem, the sentence related to the funding source and the number of the Grant Agreement) have been designed and made available for all partners. Finalized communication tools have been shared through the LENSES website (see “Communication and Dissemination Tools” in the [Outcomes](#) web section) as well as via social media, ready to be used. On the other hand, the same communication and dissemination tools have been made available for all partners, in editable format, in the dedicated “[Partner area](#)” accessible upon registration. Communication products have been used by all partners in English language or translated into local languages depending on the type of target audience. In the sessions below, a detailed description of all tools prepared for communication and dissemination purposes, together with information on where to view or download them, are provided.

The C&D toolkit comprises the following C&D Tools:

- ❖ General project brochure;
- ❖ General project Power point;
- ❖ General project poster;

- ❖ General project roll-up;
- ❖ Project roll-up with partners logos;
- ❖ Lenses one-pager

2.4 Publications

Publications should be easy to read and understand. The most important thing is that they convey the right information about the project to the right target group. The format of the content should vary in order to keep readers attracted (use of boxes, bullet points, graphics, etc.). The quantity of information that can be conveyed in the space available must be considered carefully, to avoid fully covered pages. It is also very important to choose the right graphics and imagery. A good use of photos will enhance the visibility both of the printed materials and of website. A choice of photos related to the project topic will be made available in the project Files repository. Particular attention is advised to consider possible copyrights carefully.

LENSES publications are planned mainly in the final project phase, as they will illustrate and disseminate the project results. Nevertheless, a number of publications has been already published at the time in which this deliverable has been released, and are made available for the wide public in various sections of the project website. The following sections gives additional details on the contents of LENSES publications produced so far and on the virtual spaces where they have been archived.

2.4.1 *Scientific products*

According to the grant agreement, Art. **29.1 Obligation to disseminate results**, “unless it goes against their legitimate interests”, each project partner will, as soon as possible, ‘**disseminate**’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

Project partners will strongly promote the scientific exploitation of the project results. All generated data (subject to privacy and GDPR agreements) and methodologies will be shared and provided to the research community for further exploring the potential of use of the LENSES approaches. All relevant research outputs (e.g. evaluation data, papers, case studies, co-creation models) will be released **on an open access basis** (free of charge, online access for any user) in peer-reviewed journals (**Art.29.2 Open access to scientific publications**). Moreover, the LENSES research partners will consider alternatives for exploiting the project results for scientific and research purposes, e.g. for educational/training purposes or under new research projects.

The scientific products published in the context of LENSES will be made available for the wide public in the section “Outcomes” of the project website and, more specifically, in the right column of the page “[Communication and Dissemination Tools](#)”.

2.4.2 *Other publications*

Pilot related communication and dissemination products

All communication and dissemination products related to each specific pilot area have been made available in the project website, in the pilot related webpage and, more specifically, in the sub-section “pilot related documents”. This section includes documents written both in English and in local language, with the aim to raise the awareness of local stakeholders both on the project and on the activities carried out within the national pilot area.

National press releases

Other not-scientific publications, released along the project lifespan by each single partner institution, will be archived and made available for the wide public in the [Partner section](#) of the project website, in the sub-section “Press release” present in the webpage dedicated to each specific partner institutions. These publications are commonly released in local language for the benefits of national stakeholders.

3. Events

3.1 Plenary and regional meetings

Plenary and regional meetings will be organized to support communication and collaboration both within the project family and with the stakeholder community, as well as training (e.g. targeted to consortium members in the skills needed for pilot area implementation of each WP and to stakeholders in the use of LENSES data products and tools) and dissemination (Table 3). The Regional meetings rely on personal contacts and cannot be replaced with virtual meetings (unless absolutely necessary as identified in project risks, see Covid19). In contrast, Plenary meetings of the technical WP teams and most WP leaders meetings can be more easily confined to virtual meetings both to reduce travel cost and to overcome travel restrictions established due to COVID-19 pandemic at the time of the project launch (May 2021). Therefore, all working meetings will be held virtually, exception made for a first one, to allow project members to meet in person at least one time.

Although the kick of meeting was initially foreseen to be held in person, then it was held online because of restrictions for international travel, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. LENSES partners met for the first time in person at the 2nd plenary meeting, which was held in Rome from 23 to 25 May 2022.

Table 3 Meeting plan, approximate dates and tentative locations.

Type of meeting	Month	Attendance
Kick-off Meeting – (virtual because of travel restrictions due to COVID-19 pandemic)	M1 – held on 31st May and 1st June 2021	All partners, External Advisory Board (EAB), PRIMA PO and Financial manager
1st Plenary Meeting (virtual)	M6 – held on 13 Dec 2021	All partners, EAB, EC
1st Regional Meeting (one in each pilot area)	M6-M10	All partners of same pilot + LAA stakeholders
2nd Plenary Meeting (Hybrid event: in Rome and online) + 1 st Trans-Regional Meeting	M12 –held in Rome from 23 to 25 May 2022	All partners, LAA stakeholders (all pilots), EAB, EC
2nd Regional Meeting (one in each pilot area)	M14-M16	All partners of same pilot + LAA stakeholders
3rd Plenary Meeting (virtual)	M18	All partners, EAB, EC

3 rd Regional Meeting (one in each pilot area)	M20-M22	All partners of same pilot + LAA stakeholders
4 th Plenary Meeting + 2 nd Trans-Regional Meeting (to be held in person, most probably in Jordan and Israel)	M24	All partners, LAA stakeholders (all pilots), EAB, EC, external invitees
4 th Regional Meeting (one in each pilot area)	M26-M28	All partners of same pilot + LAA stakeholders
5 th Plenary Meeting (virtual)	M30	All partners, EAB, EC
5 th Regional Meeting (one in each pilot area)	M32-M34	All partners of same pilot + LAA stakeholders
Final (6 th) Plenary Meeting (tbd)	M36	All partners, EAB, EC

The regional meetings are participatory activities involving the broad group of stakeholders in each pilot area. A tentative planning for these meetings was presented and discussed with the pilot leaders in an intra-project LAA meeting and is represented in Figure 6 . The generic distribution of participatory activities includes: i) a 1st Regional Meeting (LAA kick-off meeting) for introducing the project and co-identifying the main sectoral objectives and challenges (although in some pilots this was substituted by a round of interviews including a project presentation); ii) a series of three workshops whose contents need to be aligned with the selected objectives for each pilot; iii) and a final workshop or dissemination activity focusing on presenting results and identifying next steps and follow-up actions.

5 "Regional Meetings" (tentative timeline and content)

Figure 6 Generic planning for the LENSES Regional Meetings

3.2 Webinars

Webinars will be organized in the context of Task 9.3 “Dissemination and communication actions”, under the coordination CREA and with the participation of all project partners (M20-30). **2 Nexus e-dialogue webinars** will disseminate the results and lessons learned from the LENSES approach in the pilot sites, in partnership with LAAs (WP2) and pilots (WP8). In addition, **2 webinars** will focus more on the technical aspects of the activities implemented in the pilot areas and discuss replication potential in different contexts. All the materials shared during the webinars (e.g., power point presentation) will be made available on the project website. Furthermore, all webinars will be recorded and the recording will share both on the LENSES YouTube channel and via the project website.

3.3 Closing event

The closing event will be organized in the context of Task 9.3 “Dissemination and communication actions”, under the coordination of CREA and with the participation of all project partners, on M34 (February 2024). The closing event will feature LENSES case studies, their results and their exploitation potential also through the related business plan. The event will be held online to reduce financial and environmental costs and to increase outreach. All the materials shared during the closing event (e.g., power point presentation) will be made available on the project website. Furthermore, the event will be recorded and the recording will shared both on the LENSES YouTube channel and via the project website.

4. Resources

4.1 Human resources

WP9 is entirely dedicated to Communication and Dissemination actions. Dr. Tiziana Pirelli (CREA) has led this Work Package in which all PPs have been directly involved, although into varying degree. The human resources identified for the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination activities foreseen within the LENSES project have been specified in the “PRIMA - Technical annex (Part II)” of the Grant Agreement, session 3.1.4 “Description of each work package”, “WP9: Pathways to impact”.

5. Final remarks

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy has taken into account the instructions shared by the PRIMA Foundation Project Officer during the kick-off meeting.

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy is meant to be a “living document”. Therefore, it will be integrated and updated in the course of the project lifespan, according to the needs and opportunities that

will emerge during the implementation of the Action. It will benefit of PPs' contributions as well as of the results achieved in other project activities.

6. References

LENSES Grant Agreement

LENSES Consortium Agreement between the CREA and the LENSES partners

Pinnacle, "Project Communication Guide – INTERREG IVC Programme", 2012 release

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